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Archaeological Findings in the Finalese Area and the Birth of Religion in Prehistory.

Alfredo Pirondini writes: A large number of archaeological sites and artefacts dating back to prehistoric times in the Finale Ligure area (Western Liguria) are due to the appearance of the first manifestations of human religious behaviour. The author, in light of these finds, analyses the primitive roots of religious phenomenon.

As described in a masterly way by the works of Luigi Giussani (Refs 14 and 15), the religious factor is an integral part of the true nature of man. In other words, it coincides with the "ineradicable and irrepressible" questions such as, "What is the meaning of life, pain and death?" and "Why is it worth living?".

These questions are the ontological foundation of life and man has always tried to relate to the lives of creatures destined to die, within the total meaning of life itself. In archaeological research conducted in the area of Finale Ligure by the Author of this work, the encounter with the religious factor has confirmed the view taken by Giussani: since the beginning of existence, man has had a relationship with the mystery of the Godhead.

The Finale area is unique. From a geological point of view, the high frequency of karst features (with the formation of natural cavities - [see an explanation here](#)) made the landscape attractive to early man and the region has been occupied for about 350,000 years

The discovery of hand axes and stone tools also called "bifaces" from Plateau of Manie and Grotta delle Fate settlements dates back to the presence of Homo Erectus. The Grotta delle Fate and the Arma (a Ligurian term to indicate a cave) delle Manie have also yielded the skeletal remains of Homo Neanderthalensis who lived during the Middle Paleolithic (120,000 to 38,000 years ago).

The first signs of religious behaviour are seen with the Neanderthals in the forms of the burial of their dead which took place in the caves themselves. The graves were oval in shape and covered with stone slabs. This ritual behaviour demonstrates the respect of these primitive men for death. The simultaneous presence of buried objects of daily life (food, stone tools, and jewels with engraved decorations) and red ochre (that recalls the blood, as a vital element), could represent the hope of a new life, after the death of the body.

About 38,000 years ago in the Upper Paleolithic, during the last great glaciation that marked the extinction of Neanderthals, Homo Sapiens appeared. In the cave of Arene Candide, several graves were found, including the most famous of them, the "Young Prince" (dating back to 24,000 years ago), so named for the rich outfit that accompanied this very young man into the afterlife. In the Neolithic Age (which grew, in Liguria, from 5,800 to 3,600 BC.) there was a big change in society from man the nomadic hunter and gatherer, to man the farmer and rancher.

Better control of natural resources made man sedentary, it led to an increase in population with the

simultaneous change in social organization and the introduction of the concept of "property". In less than 2,000 years, man's life changed more significantly than during the previous 2 million years. a radical mutation had taken place, known as the "Neolithic Revolution".

In the Ligurian Riviera, these changes are set out, according to recent observations (See Refs 3, 5, 6, 12, 21, 23 and 27) for the presumable migration of new peoples from south and central Italy. The archaeological finds at Arene Candide, Arma della Pollera and, quite recently, at Pian del Ciliegio Rock Shelter (Manie Plateau) date mostly from the period of "Impressed Ware Culture" (Early Neolithic: 5,800 to 5,000 BC) and "Square-Mouthed Pottery Culture" (Middle Neolithic: 5,000 to 4,200 BC). They are associated with cults and rituals that developed in the Mediterranean Basin, connected to the reproduction and growth of plants and animals. The discovery of female figurines would seem in fact to be allied to propitiation of the fertility of the land and flocks (6).

From 4th millennium BC, man increased his knowledge concerning the processing of metalliferous minerals. Following the development of metallurgy, communities were organized into increasingly complex structures, with a true hierarchy. Hillforts (see Photo 1, above), known as Castellieri or Castellari, were built in high places. In Finalese these have been well studied, for example the [Hillfort of Verezzi](#), Castelliere delle Anime on Rocca di Perti, Sant'Antonino and Monte Sant'Elena above Bergeggi.

Distinct ethnic identities were defined, linked to quite distinct geographical areas. In North Western Italy and in Southern France, between the Middle Bronze Age (about 1,600 BC) and early Iron Age (about 900 BC) a new civilisation appeared, the Ancient Ligurians, one of the ethnic groups of pre-Roman Italy. Since the end of the fifth millennium, at the end of the third millennium BC (a period covering the Neolithic and Bronze Age), there developed a civilization related to the cult of stone. Megalithic buildings were erected. Single and/or aligned Menhirs, Dolmens and Cromlechs (megalithic fences). The presence of such structures is often related to areas of engraved rocks which are believed to be contemporary.

The significance of this proximity could be explained as a sign of the presence of the "sacral". In this regard, the engraving of "prayers" confirm this hypothesis. Cups and gutters may have been used as containers and liquid collectors (organic and / or metaphoric) for ritual purposes (7), (8), (9), (10), (11). The "cruciforms", may have been on the other hand, signs of Christianization and as such, be ascribed to more recent times. This would confirm the usage of these sites even in Roman, Medieval and perhaps even more recent Ages, with the original purpose of recognising sacred areas.

With the Iron Age (that, in Liguria, developed between 900 and 180 BC) the stele statues (or anthropomorphic steles) made their appearance. These standing stones with engravings are well represented in the Lunigiana (Eastern Liguria). Currently, the only example, found in the Finalese area, of this artifact is the rudimentary stele of Pila delle Penne (Photos 3 and 4 below).

According to the most current theories, the veneration and religious observances of prehistoric man were directed to the peaks of mountains, springs, rivers, trees, weather phenomena (thunder and lightning) and to the celestial bodies, especially the sun and the moon.

In Finalese, astronomically oriented structures are present e.g. "Observatory" of Bric Pianarella, Menhir and Dolmen of Verezzi, Dolmen of Monticello, Rocks, and other Altar tables present on the highest peaks of the area (Altars of Monte Cucco, Rocca degli Uccelli, Bric del Frate, [Arma Strapatente](#), Bric of Sant'Antonino).

All of these megalithic structures, as previously described, are in close proximity to widely known engraved rocks known as Ciappu de Cunche (i.e. Ciappo delle Conche. The term "Ciappo" in the Finale means a large slab of stone), the Ciappu de Cunchette (i.e. Ciappu dei Cexi or Ciappo dei Ceci), the Ciappu du Sá (i.e. Ciappo del Sale), Ciappo della Valle dei Frassini - to name only the largest - with the presence of prayers, crosses, cups and gutters (see Photo 2 below).

The dating of these archaeological remains is not unique. The existence of other similar structures in the European area is well known.

We remember, in fact, what has been reported in numerous studies that refer to the sanctuary of Panoias, (Northern Portugal). Here, beside a large rock with ponds, canals and cups, there is the following Latin inscription dating from the third century AD (11):

"HUIUS HOSTIAE QUAE CADUNT HIC IMM(ol)ANTUR EXTRA INTRA QUADRATA CONTRA CREMANTUR - SAN(gu)IS LAC(i)CULIS (iuxta) SUPERFU(ndi)TUR".

Loosely translated as "Here the slaughtered victims are consecrated to the Gods: their entrails are burnt

in the square ponds and their blood is diffused along the surrounding small ponds.”

Large rocky outcrops, with characteristics similar to those described for the sanctuary of Panoias, in the Finale, could, at least for a certain period, have had a similar function. Moreover, the fact that the "altar-stones" are built on high ground likely indicates the desire to choose an appropriate site to have a visual appreciation of the panoramic vista of the land below, also in relation to the sacredness of the hill stations and mountain peaks, typical of the Ligurian-Celtic populations.

Dolmens and Menhirs are not therefore unrelated to the Finalese and sub-alpine cultural area, as was thought until a few decades ago (See Photos 6 and 7 below, and [Photo 5, linked here](#)).

It was believed that the megalithic culture had been arrested in the Alps region, without crossing the Alps. The only exception was the Pugliese area (Southern Italy), where dolmens, menhirs, specchie (i.e. mounds of stones) were attributed instead to the influence of people from the Balkan Peninsula across the Adriatic Sea, while in the rest of the Mediterranean basin, the megalithic culture is well represented. Puglisi's work: "La civiltà appenninica. Origine delle comunità pastorali in Italia" (25) in 1959 and the discovery a few years later of the Neolithic necropolis of Aosta, proved the unfounded nature of this thesis (See Refs 4, 7, 8, 9 and 10).

Regarding the Liguria, in the second half of the eighties of the last century, in the northern Sanremo hinterland (Imperia Province), two circular burial mounds were identified. One of them, studied with stratigraphic methods from the local section of the International Institute of Ligurian Studies, has been attributed to the final phase of the Bronze Age (Ref 1).

The penetration of megalithic culture in this Region was thus demonstrated, presumably from the nearby Provence. Consequently, other artefacts found in Liguria, especially in the area of Finale (just mention the Menhir and Dolmen of Verezzi), until then attributed with reservations to the recent rural culture, took on a different meaning and the scarcity of megalithic remains in Italy, whilst differing from the transalpine regions (especially the North-Western and the islands), could be explained by the increased turnover of civilizations over time that would have radically transformed the appearance of the area, resulting in the loss of many of these artefacts (Refs 7, 8, 9, 10).

Conclusions

The concept of religion is therefore born from remotest antiquity and man has been seen to identify rituals (worship of the dead) and to recognize the sacral presence in certain geological formations (e.g. mountain peaks) or the construction of megalithic structures like Menhirs and Dolmens. These artefacts can be dated to a window of time between the end of the fifth millennium to the late third millennium BC, corresponding roughly to a period ranging from the Neolithic and through the Bronze Age (20), (26).

This length of time could correspond with that of other megaliths that have already been described by scientists and by the Author.

The precise dating of the petroglyphs and megaliths described is a difficult problem at present, because they are outdoors and can easily be modified by atmospheric and human factors.

The [Stone Altar above the Strapatente Cave](#), the other Altars or "Stone Tables" on the tops of rocky outcrops of Finalese, the so-called [Dolmen of Monticello](#) (near Finale Ligure), the rudimentary anthropomorphic Stele of Pila delle Penne, the findings of the Plateau of San Bernardino (among which the Bric Pianarella Observatory and the Archaeoastronomical Complex of Marcello Dalbuono), but also other neighboring megaliths (2),(3), (5), (6), (12), (13), (17), (20), (21), (23), (24), (27), (28),(29), represent only some examples of findings that would deserve a more detailed study in the light of modern scientific knowledge (e.g. [archaeometry](#) and archaeoastronomy, stratigraphy, geology, etc.) that could lead to important innovations in the area of Western Liguria and, especially in the Finalese.

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In Memoriam of Luigi Giussani (10.15.1922 - 02.22.2005): the seventh year of the death. "...those who lead the many to justice shall be like the stars forever."(Dan. 12,3)

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Photo 6: "Observatory" of Bric Pianarella

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Photo 4: The wall and Stele of Pila delle Penne

Archaeological Findings in the Finalese Area of NW Italy submitted by [mpwpir](#)
Photo 3: Stele at Pila delle Penne

Archaeological Findings in the Finalese Area of NW Italy submitted by [mpwpir](#)
Photo 2: Engraved rocks at Ciappu de Cunche

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Photo 7: The Stone Altar

Photo 1: Hillfort of Verezzi

Photo 2: Engraved rocks at Ciappu de Cunche

Photo 3: Stele at Pila delle Penne

Photo 4: The wall and Stele of Pila delle Penne

Photo 5: The Dolmen of Monticello

Photo 6: “Observatory” of Bric Pianarella

Photo 7: The Altar above Arma Strapatente

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